

Short name	Complexity of the CCUS value chain	Long name	Complexity of the CCUS value chain
Geographical scope	All regions		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>The CCUS value chain – CO₂ capture, CO₂ transport and CO₂ storage or utilization – is likely to involve different, and perhaps multiple, companies at each stage. This establishes cross-chain risk between the different stages of the CCS chain: for example, the CO₂ store developer needs assurance that there will be a supply of CO₂ before they will invest, while a CO₂ emitter will need to be sure there is a destination for the CO₂ before investing in carbon capture.</p> <p>This cross-chain risk may be compounded in a CCUS cluster, where there are even more organisations that need to reach agreement. CCS has historically been conceived as part of large single-source-to-single-store projects (usually applied thermal power generation using fossil fuel), but as its potential for decarbonizing many other industrial sources of CO₂ is increasingly well understood, the need for a multisectoral approach grows. This can include a shared CO₂ transport and storage system which is available for all users; and means that support for infrastructure needs to be available at a time which lines up with support for capture at individual industries.</p> <p>Additional complexity comes with projects that cross national or regional boundaries and jurisdictions: this is particularly important for the ‘ownership’ of, and long-term liability for, stored CO₂.</p> <p>Clusters will need to consider:</p> <p>Availability and maturity of permanent and temporary CO₂ storage – including whether there are companies operating in the transport and storage sector.</p> <p>Availability of CO₂ transport infrastructure: this includes pipeline and non-pipeline transport. For shipping, attention will need to be paid to the availability and suitability of ships and port infrastructure. This is being explored by the EverLoNG project¹.</p> <p>Readiness of value chain and operators – this links back to <i>Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies</i>, and issues of competition for resources, funding and skilled workers.</p> <p>Beyond these headline considerations, other issues include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing hydrogen or syngas into the gas grid, in order to create a market for gases that have been produced using CCS • Consistent approaches to CO₂ handling and CO₂ specifications across countries 		

¹ <https://everlongccus.eu>. Initial report on CO₂ shipping interoperability available here: <https://everlongccus.eu/about-the-project/results>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability of ships to handle different types of gas
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>Survey respondents highlighted the complexity of the value chain and the importance of defining project roles and responsibilities, and contractual arrangements. The uncertainty around the development of CCS and its place in the market also adds to the risks.</p> <p>Some viewed timely development of transport and storage infrastructure as the key to unlocking the economics for CCUS clusters and providing industries with the opportunity to use CCUS to decarbonise. This echoes the view of the UK's 2016 report <i>Lowest cost decarbonisation for the UK: the critical role of CCS</i>².</p>
Other issues this affects	Business models, Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evergrowing project; (n.d.): EVERLONG, https://everlongccus.eu, European Union. • Oxburgh, R.; (2016): Lowest cost decarbonisation for the UK: the critical role of CCS, https://www.research.ed.ac.uk/en/publications/oxburgh-2016-lowest-cost-decarbonisation-for-the-uk-the-critical-, United Kingdom.

² Oxburgh (2016) Lowest cost decarbonisation for the UK: the critical role of CCS. <https://www.research.ed.ac.uk/en/publications/oxburgh-2016-lowest-cost-decarbonisation-for-the-uk-the-critical->